

PCP WISE

D2.11 Project website

WP2 Impact Maximisation

G.A.C. Group

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Document abstract

The present document *D2.11 Project website* provides a description of the PCP WISE project's public website and its structure. The project website is an important dissemination tool, being one of the main channels to present PCP WISE to the project stakeholders and extended audience. It is an informative website that presents the main project information to the general public, such as the consortium, objectives and work structure, and provides link to the PCP WISE Community Platform and LinkedIn for news and updates.

Keywords

Project website ; communication; dissemination

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
PCP	Pre-Commercial Procurement
PCP WISE	Pre-Commercial Procurement for Water Intelligence from Space for European climate resilience
PDF	Portable Document Format
Q&A	Questions & Answers

1. Introduction

The PCP WISE website was launched at the end of March 2025 (M3) and is managed by the Work Package 2 leader, G.A.C. Group.

The PCP WISE website features a responsive design, ensuring optimal display across all devices, from desktop computers to mobile phones.

Serving as the project's primary dissemination channel, the website is integrated with social media and will host all public information and documentation generated throughout the project. This includes deliverables, event details and reports, newsletters, and links to relevant publication.

The website is accessible at: <https://pcp-wise.eu/>

The website serves as the primary vehicle for raising awareness of the PCP WISE project. It provides a general overview of the project's objectives and consortium while offering public information on project activities, results, events and more. Additionally, it guides stakeholders on 'How to Get Involved', grants access to the [PCP WISE Community Platform](#), and includes an option to subscribe to the project newsletter.

Designed in line with the PCP WISE branding, the website plays a key role in the project's communication and information campaign. Its content is continuously updated as new information becomes available.

To maximise outreach, the PCP WISE project also promotes and is promoted through other relevant web portals, creating synergies with other projects and initiatives such as the SPACE4CITIES, VALORADA, the Urban Agenda Partnership for Strategic and Innovation Procurement, and project partners' websites.

The project website is designed to engage all target audiences, including the public. It will provide a clear introduction to the project and its potential impact, ensuring accessibility even for those unfamiliar with the topic.

2. Content of the website

2.1. Home page

The homepage provides an introduction to PCP WISE project, outlining its mission to support climate resilience through Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP). It features a dynamic slider with three main calls to action: an invitation to learn more about the project, information on how stakeholders can participate, and details regarding the upcoming PCP WISE call for tenders. Additionally, the homepage highlights recent news' updates and displays project partner organisations' logos.

PCP WISE

About Get Involved Call for Tenders News & Events Networking Contact

WATER MANAGEMENT INNOVATIONS FOR CLIMATE RESILIENCE

Pre-commercial procurement of water management innovations from space

Learn more

Find out how to get involved and have your say in the PCP WISE project

Learn more

The PCP WISE Call for Tenders is coming up! Interested to apply?

Learn more

36 months

€19 million

26 partners

PCP WISE is a Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP) action funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Programme and selected under the call HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01-5. PCP WISE plays a key role in advancing the European Green Deal's objectives by enhancing the use of Environmental Observation (EO), data and products. The project starts in January 2025 and runs for 36 months. PCP WISE has an allocated budget of €19 million, including €12 million for financing the R&D phases of the PCP.

More about PCP-WISE →

Figure 1: Homepage (part 1)

Figure 2: Homepage (part 2)

2.2. About

The ‘About’ section delves deeper into the background, timeline and objectives of PCP WISE. This page displays the two posters of the project: the general presentation poster and the technical one. It is possible to open these posters in PDF version. This section also details the project’s consortium, listing partner organisations and their roles, as well as the structure of its five work packages. A dedicated subsection explains the concept of PCP.

PCP WISE About Get involved Call for Tenders News & Events Networking Contact

ABOUT

What is PCP WISE?

PCP WISE is a Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP) action funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Programme and selected under the call HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01-5. PCP WISE plays a key role in advancing the European Green Deal's objectives by enhancing the use of Environmental Observation (EO), data and products. The project starts in January 2025 and runs for 36 months. PCP WISE has an allocated budget of €19 million, including €12 million for financing the R&D phases of the PCP.

PCP WISE is an innovative project aimed at developing cutting-edge solutions (up to TRL 8) for water management and climate resilience across Europe using the PCP instrument. By leveraging space technology and EO data, PCP WISE seeks to address critical challenges related to floods, fires, and infrastructure impacts both in rural and urban areas. This collaborative effort brings together public buyers, research institutions, and industry experts to create and implement advanced climate services that will enhance Europe's ability to adapt to and mitigate the effects of climate change.

PCP WISE flyer, click to enlarge

The challenge

Water-related crises fuelled by climate change (flooding, wildfires, droughts, degraded water quality, soil/subsidence) are calling for urgent governments' response.

The levers

- Pre-Commercial Procurement
- Environmental Observation data
- Climate adaptation policies and strategies

The desired solution

A smart, versatile and cross-border soil-water-vegetation intelligence warning, management and monitoring systems for both rural and urban areas tailored to end-users' needs.

What is the timeline of the project?

Project official start date (Jan. 2025) | Tendering phase (Sept. 2025 - Feb. 2026) | Project official end date (Dec. 2027) | Post PCP WISE phase: Public procurement of innovative solutions

PCP Preparation phase (Jan. 2025 - Aug. 2026) | PCP Implementation phase (Mar. 2026 - Dec. 2027)

PCP WISE

The Challenge We Face: Climate Change and Water Management

Climate change is a complex and multifaceted global challenge that is driving floods, wildfires, water scarcity, droughts, and sea-level rise. These challenges are threatening the health and well-being of communities and ecosystems worldwide. The European Commission is committed to addressing these challenges through the European Green Deal and the European Climate Law. The PCP WISE project is a key part of this effort, aiming to develop innovative solutions for water management and climate resilience.

Key Challenges:

- 1. Increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events (floods, droughts, wildfires).
- 2. Growing water scarcity and stress, particularly in rural and urban areas.
- 3. Rising sea levels and coastal erosion, threatening infrastructure and communities.
- 4. Degradation of water quality and ecosystems, impacting human health and biodiversity.
- 5. Increasing pressure on water resources due to population growth and industrial activities.

Impact: The PCP WISE project is expected to have a significant impact on water management and climate resilience across Europe. It will provide innovative solutions for water management and climate resilience, helping to reduce the impact of climate change on water resources and ecosystems. The project will also create jobs and stimulate economic growth in the water and climate sectors.

Water Management from Space

A New Approach for Global Climate Challenges

PCP WISE: Maximizing the Soil-Water-Vegetation System

PCP WISE focuses on maximizing the health of the soil-water-vegetation system, which is essential for water management and climate resilience. The project will develop innovative solutions for water management and climate resilience, including:

- 1. Soil moisture monitoring: Using satellite data to monitor soil moisture levels, which is essential for water management and climate resilience.
- 2. Vegetation indices: Using satellite data to monitor vegetation health, which is essential for water management and climate resilience.
- 3. Water stress detection: Using satellite data to detect water stress in vegetation, which is essential for water management and climate resilience.
- 4. Flood detection: Using satellite data to detect floods, which is essential for water management and climate resilience.
- 5. Drought detection: Using satellite data to detect droughts, which is essential for water management and climate resilience.

PCP WISE Action Plan

The PCP WISE action plan consists of several key activities, including:

- 1. Developing innovative solutions for water management and climate resilience.
- 2. Conducting research and development in the field of water management and climate resilience.
- 3. Implementing pilot projects to test the effectiveness of the developed solutions.
- 4. Disseminating the results of the project to the wider community.
- 5. Establishing a network of experts and stakeholders to support the project.

Benefits for Water Authorities

Water authorities are responsible for managing water resources and ensuring that water is available for all. The PCP WISE project offers several benefits for water authorities, including:

- 1. Improved water management: Using satellite data to monitor water resources and manage them more effectively.
- 2. Increased climate resilience: Using satellite data to detect and respond to climate change impacts on water resources.
- 3. Reduced costs: Using satellite data to optimize water management and reduce costs.
- 4. Increased transparency: Using satellite data to provide transparent information to the public about water resources and management.
- 5. Improved decision-making: Using satellite data to make better decisions about water management and climate resilience.

Costs for Governments are increasing

The cost of climate change is increasing rapidly, with estimates reaching €13.4 billion per year by 2030. This is due to the increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, rising sea levels, and the degradation of water resources. Governments are therefore facing increasing costs for disaster relief, infrastructure damage, and the loss of water resources.

Climate goals together through the use of smart monitoring

The PCP WISE project is a key part of the European Green Deal and the European Climate Law. It aims to help governments achieve their climate goals by using smart monitoring technologies. This includes using satellite data to monitor water resources, vegetation health, and climate change impacts. By using this data, governments can make better decisions about water management and climate resilience, and reduce the impact of climate change on water resources and ecosystems.

Dynamic satellite data combined with local data takes water management to 'the next level'

The PCP WISE project is using dynamic satellite data combined with local data to take water management to the next level. This includes using satellite data to monitor water resources, vegetation health, and climate change impacts. By combining this data with local data, water authorities can get a more complete picture of water resources and management, and make better decisions about water management and climate resilience.

From Water board to information board

The PCP WISE project is helping water authorities move from being just water boards to becoming information boards. This is done by using satellite data to provide transparent information to the public about water resources and management. This information can be used to help the public make better decisions about water use and conservation, and to hold water authorities accountable for their actions.

PCP WISE flyer, click to enlarge

Figure 3: 'About' page

2.3. Get involved

The 'Get Involved' page invites stakeholders to engage with the project through the PCP WISE Community Platform and the Stakeholder Observatory Group.

Figure 4: 'Get involved' page

2.4. Call for Tenders

The 'Call for Tenders' section is designed to inform potential suppliers about the upcoming PCP WISE procurement opportunities. It introduces the planned call for tenders and also outlines the project's key challenges and use cases, although detailed content is still under development. Subsections include a forthcoming Open Market Consultation page, a Q&A section, and a matchmaking platform, which will assist suppliers in forming consortia for joint tender submissions.

Figure 5: 'Call for tenders' page

2.5. News & Events

The 'News & Events' section combines project updates with details about upcoming events. It provides stakeholders with the latest developments in PCP WISE and offers an option to subscribe to the project's newsletter for regular updates. The section is structured to present news articles alongside a calendar of future events in a clear and accessible manner.

NEWS & EVENTS

Latest News

PCP WISE STAKEHOLDER SPOTLIGHT

Today with **Barrabés**

Project coordinator

Lisa Laparra Gil (Project Manager), Raquel Beneyto Carve (Social Coordinator), Anaïs Mª Salvador (Innovation Coordinator), Mica Livinsky (Lead Procurement)

PCP WISE Stakeholder spotlight – Today with Barrabés!

Who are the PCP WISE partners driving innovation in water [...]

[Read More >](#)

PCP WISE STAKEHOLDER SPOTLIGHT

Today with **Het Waterschapshuis**

Lead Procurer

Armed Engelen (Procurement & Contract Manager), Beate Engel (Contract Lead), Peter Karmann (Lead Procurement)

PCP WISE Stakeholder spotlight – Today with Het Waterschapshuis!

Who are the PCP WISE partners driving innovation in water [...]

[Read More >](#)

Upcoming Events

PCP WISE

Join the PCP WISE Webstival – Shaping the Future of Water Innovation!

This April 2025, the PCP WISE Webstival is bringing together [...]

[Read More >](#)

Figure 6: 'News & Events' page

2.6. Networking

The 'Networking' page highlights collaborations with other European projects, including PROTECT, SPACE4CITIES, and VALORADA. Other projects and initiatives will be added throughout the project's lifetime.

Figure 7: 'Networking' page

2.7. Contact

The 'Contact' page provides essential contact details, including an inquiry form and an email address for direct communication: info-PCP-Wise(a)group-gac.com.

CONTACT

Name

Email

Subject

Message

I have read and accepted the [Privacy Policy](#). Your data will be processed by G.A.C. Group, PCP WISE Data Officer, in compliance with the provisions of the GDPR

SEND

Project Manager

Mélissa Campagno
G.A.C. Group
Sophia Antipolis, France
info-PCP-Wise(a)group-gac.com

Figure 8: 'Contact' page